

SOCIAL-PSYCHOLOGICAL GOALS AND DUTIES OF MAN IN THE CONCEPT OF THE HEART BY CARL JUNG

Asatulloev Inomjon Abobakir Ugli

Associate Professor of Fergana State University,

Doctor of Philosophy (PhD)

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10714690>

Abstract: This article analyzes the socio-psychological goals and duties of a person in Carl Jung's concept of the soul.

Key words: soul, soul, spirit, spiritual power, human soul, spiritual world, psyche, philosophical anthropology.

Carl Gustav Jung was born in Switzerland in 1875. All his paternal relatives were church ministers, and he was brought up in the spirit of Calvinist traditions from a young age. In his autobiography, K. Jung notes that religion played a major role in his teenage imagination. From a very young age, he observes about God, about his creation, "God consists of immediate ideas beyond any discussion"[1], he says. The religious environment has a great influence on Jung's worldview, and in many ways has a determining importance in his scientific work, professional interests, and research. Despite this, he breaks family traditions and chooses the path of medicine.

As Jung turned to psychiatry (psychology), he also founded "psychological analysis". He relied on medical practice and philosophical teachings in the theoretical development of his views. The scientist had a deep knowledge of Western philosophy. He was also interested in Eastern philosophy. He especially knew the essence of the ideas of Taoism and Buddhism. Jung wrote in his memoirs that from a young age he was devoted to the study of philosophical ideas. In the end, he thinks for a long time about which field to choose - philosophy or medicine? But even though he chose medicine, his interest in philosophy never faded. "Despite the fact that my scientific interests were more focused on medicine," Jung wrote in his memoirs, "I occasionally returned to philosophy"[1]. Especially the views of philosophers such as Plato, I. Kant, A. Schopenhauer, E. Hartmann and F. Nietzsche attracted the scientist's attention.

In 1900, K. Jung graduated from the Faculty of Medicine of the University of Basel and began working at a psychiatric hospital in Zurich. Studying the phenomenon of the split personality, he approaches the problem of the unconscious. At this time, there was almost no deep scientific theory of the unconscious in philosophy. And the ideas of A. Schopenhauer and E. Hartmann were too abstract to philosophically illuminate concrete medical data. He was unable to clarify the issue that directly interested him.

Jung made a firm decision, chose his own path, and created his own independent school, starting with the revision of a number of fundamental principles of earlier psychoanalysis. In particular, they include the nature of libido (sexual desire), the structure of the unconscious, periods of personality development, and a number of other issues. He criticizes Freud's exaggeration of lustful and spiritual purity (pathological) aspects of the psyche, his interpretation of culture as a product of repressed lust, his misunderstanding of

the true nature of religion, and others. But in the middle of this separation lay a worldview of a very deep nature.

K. Jung leads a long, creatively rich life. Possession of wide knowledge, sharp memory, knowledge of several languages, pursuit of multifaceted scientific interests expanded the boundaries of the scientist's research possibilities. He has more than seventeen volumes of works devoted to many aspects of philosophy, religion, mythology, alchemy, astrology, and cultural history, in addition to his personal psychological studies. "In my imagination," writes K. Jung, "I seem to be working on the border of exact sciences, collecting evidence, observing, classifying, interpreting causal and significant relationships." I come to the conclusion that sometimes I seem to get wrapped up in deep reflections that go beyond the limits of natural knowledge and pass into the fields of philosophy, theology, comparative theology and social sciences as a whole"[2].

Thus, Carl Jung relies on practical medical experiences and the philosophy of the past in his theoretical views. It is also known that he was better acquainted with Western philosophy, besides, he was very interested in Eastern philosophy, especially Taoism and Buddhism, and made deep analytical conclusions. According to the scientist, philosophy occupies a large place in his worldview. He was especially influenced by the teachings of Plato, I. Kant, A. Schopenhauer, E. Hartmann and F. Nietzsche [3]. These forced him to critically review the views of his predecessors and focus on clinical practice.

According to the German psychologists F. Lange, I. Müller and O. Schuman, a certain skill is formed in a person as a result of repeating the same actions many times. Through this skill, a certain external influence is received and responded to. F. Ebbinghaus compares the skill in a person with the mental state of an individual that occurs when performing a routine action. Similarly, Jung understood by skill the movement of the psyche in a certain direction and the response to it. The concept of skill is very necessary to reveal the complex inner phenomena of the human psyche. Under the influence of this, behavior appears in a certain way.

What changes from a psychoanalytic point of view in the activity that calls a person to action by introducing the concept of skills in the person? First of all, Jung criticizes the idea that the subconscious activity of a person in the classic psychoanalysis is determined by greed, and says that it is not greed, but the skill to which any activity is subordinate [4]. In addition, the scientist tries to demonstrate with the help of skill that there is no conflict between consciousness and unconsciousness, on the contrary, they require each other. Based on this situation, the scientist distinguishes unconscious and conscious skills. Such a duality replaces the dependent balance of the psyche: that is, the activity of the unconscious balances the conscious skill, and the activity of the mind, on the contrary, maintains the balance of the unconscious skill. "I specifically use the word 'complementary', not 'opposition,'" writes Jung, "because consciousness and unconsciousness are not always in conflict, but rather they complement each other." Together they form a whole. This wholeness manifests itself"[4]. Identity, in our view, ensures that a person has a coherent idea and ideology. Because the self is the totality of the skill thought by K. Jung in Eastern philosophy.

Analyzing the problem of skills, Jung says that a person tends to take into account objective and subjective factors in order to perform specific actions. The scientist includes the innate qualities, qualities, skills acquired in the process of upbringing, the influence of the social environment, individual thoughts and collective imaginations among such factors that

seriously affect the mood. According to Jung, such factors determine the general ability of a person, and this in turn leads to a change in the interaction of the psyche in various tasks.

In addition to general skills, Jung also talks about external (extraverted) and internal (introverted) skills[5]. This leads him to the mental classification of the spiritual manifestations of a person. The need to divide personality into different (types) was formed before Jung. In his time, F. Bacon, "it is necessary to clearly and skillfully separate the specific side and generality of human characters, which helps to reveal the secret of every single talent and skill." On the basis of this knowledge, it is possible to choose the correct treatment for the heart" [6], he said.

Theoretically, external conditions and internal inclinations, according to Jung, have the same effect on the behavior of external and internal systems. In practice, internal and external circumstances tend to favor one of the systems and constrain the other. As a result, one part of the scale becomes heavier and a habit is formed. Human behavior and interests are more conditioned by external objects or connected to his internal subjective habits. It is this habitual skill that underlies the classification of types of spirituality. Thus, Jung shows three important general theoretical aspects in his analysis of the question of skill.

First, the concept of skill enters the theoretical teaching of "analytical psychology". Through this concept, Jung tries to explain the nature of unconsciousness, more precisely, the interaction between consciousness and unconsciousness, the factors of human behavior, certain mental states of a person, and the organizational levels of his psyche. The phenomena of human cultural life are also studied by means of skills, creative activity is compared with internal skills, which have a "creative" character. Religion is also understood as a kind of spiritual skill, and it adapts to the external and internal world as a monad.

Second, by using the concept of "skill", Jung tries to expand the boundaries that define the human psyche. In classical psychoanalysis, the determination of the cause of the direction of internal mental processes was carried out only with the help of the unconscious. That is, any mental action is explained only and mainly through the action of another level of the psyche. In "analytical psychology", the concept of skill gives an opportunity to determine the interaction between objective, external conditions and the subjective internal habits of a person. In this respect, the interpretation of Jung's skills is somewhat different from the views of 19th century psychologists. The fact is that in the experimental experimental psychology of that time, the skill was compared with the level of individual-personal, internal suffering, that is, the internal subjective determinants of the human psyche took priority. Jung focuses on the external situation without denying the internal direction of human action. In this, the movement of the psyche in a certain direction is determined. Emphasizing this objective basis in all aspects, the scientist shows the difference of his teaching from the analysis of psyche based on "individual psychology".

In fact, only the unconscious was emphasized, the object of research (client, observed) could not consciously participate in the treatment process, everything was at the discretion of the psychoanalyst, the observer. And the state of skill changes this picture, because here the external - objective situation is also taken into account. The basis of the analysis is the conscious mental participation of the observed and the observer. Jung bases his theoretical concept on the "subjective conscious psychology of the individual", as a certain solid

foundation is formed accordingly. This comes in handy when justifying the spiritual law of the unconscious" [5].

Thirdly, Jung's interpretation of the concept of skill takes into account the objective and subjective aspects of the factors that determine the human psyche. In this context, it is possible to agree with Jung's statement about the objective foundations of "analytical psychology". But the scientist's thoughts and goals do not coincide with the result. There is a conflict between its theoretical and practical aspects. From this point of view, the psychology of fine skills takes on a completely different tone. It turns out to be the opposite of what Jung aspired to.

Looking at the objective situation and the subjective factors of a person in the performance of certain actions, Jung believes that the subjective factor has a greater influence on the general skill of a person. Compared to the objective factor, which is prone to change, the subjective factor, which is always monad to itself, has more basis than external objects. In addition, according to Jung, the world cannot exist for itself, it cannot exist as an objective reality, on the contrary, it is how a person perceives it. There is no object outside the subject, the world exists only because the subject exists.

It follows that in the psychology of skills, subjective habits are important in determining the tendency. "The decisive role," says Jung, "is not the feeling of reality, but the validity of the subjective factor." It is the first impressions that are collected and reflected in the mirror of the spiritual world" [5]. From the outside, Jung's "analytical psychology" calls for an objective study of the laws of the human psyche, and this approach seems to oppose the subjectivity of psychoanalysis, but in fact, it is focused on subjective factors and the unconscious, and does not stray far from Freud's teaching.

References:

1. Юнг К.Г. Вспоминания, сновидения, размышления. –Минск: Харвест, 2003. – С. 73.
2. Jung C.G. The Spirit of Psychology // In: Spirit and Nature. –L., 1955. –P. 426.
3. Jung C.G. Letters. Selected and ed. by G.Adler in collab with A.Jaffe. Vol. 2. –New Jersey, 1975. –P. 500-501.
4. Jung C.G. Two Essays on Analitical Psychology. –P. 184.
5. Юнг. К.Г. Психологические типы. –М., 1982. –С. 14, 66.
6. Бэкон Ф. Соч. В двух томах. Т. 1. –М., 1971. –С. 425.